

RELIGION'S CAPACITY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY.

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To cite this article: *Faike Usanmaz, Volume 4, No. 6-3, 2022, p. 300-319. - 0099-0001-2207-0203*

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

Religion's capacity to connect a person to both a community and a higher power is one of its primary benefits that can contribute to psychological stability. The link between spirituality and well-being is getting increased attention. According to the findings of a study conducted in the United States, regular participation in religious activities was associated with improvement in individuals' health habits, mental health, and social interactions. A separate study was conducted in Uganda, and the findings of this study showed that religious activity was linked to drug addiction. The results of this study showed that patients who scored higher on the religiosity scale had a higher rate of adherence to antiretroviral drugs. Due to the diversity of cultural and religious perspectives that exist in Asia, it is difficult to generalize about the impact of patients' cultural and religious orientations on their perceptions of social support and adherence to treatment. It would be helpful to explore the cultural and religious orientations of the Malaysian people, as well as their relationship to social support and medication adherence, as Malaysia is a multiethnic country with a diverse collection of Asian populations, including Malays, Chinese, and Indians. In Malaysia, the world's three leading religions—Islam, Christianity, and Buddhism—are practiced by a sizable portion of the population, and there is a strong correlation between religious beliefs and racial identity.

Keywords: *Religion, Religious Activities, Cultural and Religious Orientations, Beliefs and Racial Identity*

1. Introduction

When trying to identify variables that contribute to poor medication adherence, it can be helpful to be aware of the impact of cultural and religious orientations on social support and their

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relationship to medication adherence. Demographic data and treatment information; perceived cultural orientation regarding decisions regarding treatment seeking and drug use; perceived religious orientation; perceived social support; and perceived drug compliance behavior. Patients' religious orientation is assessed using a questionnaire divided into three main categories. These categories include patients' participation in organized religious activities, participation in unorganized religious activities, and intrinsic religiosity. Questions about organizational religious activities are used to determine how often patients attend public religious activities, such as religious services, or how often they participate in other religious activities affiliated with groups. Activities that patients perform privately, such as praying, reading scriptures, or watching or listening to religious programs on television or radio, are examples of non-institutional religious activities. The level of personal religious commitment or drive is measured by the concept of "intrinsic religiosity." Patients with human immunodeficiency virus have also been shown to have a significant effect on patients' adherence to medications. Different study populations (for example, the current study focused on patients with chronic disease rather than the general population); patients were asked to indicate their perceptions of certain behaviors related to seeking treatment and taking medication; and the study site included only patients who lived in urban areas and were reported to have more individualistic people.

Persons in lower positions often follow instructions or orders given to them by persons in higher positions, such as doctors, and may not want to oppose the choices made by those in higher positions. According to the findings of previous studies, there is a relationship between an elevated level of agreement between patients and doctors about the health problems and management of patients and an elevated level of adherence to medication. The quality of the relationship between patients and doctors also plays a role in drug compliance. In these studies, patients who achieved a higher degree of patient-doctor agreement and indicated that prescribers knew themselves as a person were more likely to adhere to their medication regimen. This outcome includes perceived social support only as seeking treatment and/or medication use, such as sharing joys and sorrows, sources of comfort, and resources where people can talk about their difficulties. A previous study found that among the factors used to measure the effect of social support on adherence to medication, practical support, such as reminding to take medications, had the greatest impact on patients' adherence. According to the

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findings of the study, the risk of non-adherence was found to be relative in patients who did not receive practical support, twice the risk found in patients who received such support. Only age, organizational religious activity, duration of treatment, and patients with human immunodeficiency virus were found to be crucial factors in modeling adherence to drug therapy. The Relationship Between Psychological and Physiological Disorders and Religion and Belief Patients' perceptions of the severity and susceptibility of the disease, barriers, and difficulties in taking the drug, and the benefit/cost of the drug are reported as factors that may affect patient compliance. Psychological factors such as these are also reported as factors that may affect the compliance of patients to drug therapy. A patient's degree of health literacy, patient-physician connection, and health system-related characteristics are some of the other factors that can contribute to medication adherence. However, patients' social and economic conditions, such as the availability of social support and the cost of prescriptions, as well as patients' religious views, may play a role in patients' drug compliance behavior.

2. An Exchange of Resources Between Two People

One definition of social support is "an exchange of resources between two people that appears to be aimed at improving the well-being of the recipient, either by the giver or the recipient". It is possible for social support to have a positive impact on patients' health outcomes through many different mechanisms. Some of these mechanisms are increasing patient adherence to prescribed treatments and perceptions of quality of life; decreased levels of depressive affect; facilitating better access and utilization of health services; and improving stress buffering through enhanced psychological, neuroendocrine, nutritional, or immunological functions. Social support can have a positive effect on patients' health outcomes. According to the findings of a meta-analysis conducted by Dimatteo, provision of social support, whether viewed from a practical, emotional, or dimensionless perspective, has been shown to significantly affect patients' compliance with prescription drugs. Other studies have also revealed the positive effect of social support on the patient's ability to adhere to the medication regimen. However, these studies have been conducted on Western communities that may have diverse cultural elements, religious orientations, and perceptions of the importance of social support from Asian cultures. Culture can be defined as "the collection of patterns of behavior associated with ideas, attitudes

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and actions that the people of a society share and pass on to future generations". What distinguishes one group of people from another is their culture, which includes commonalities such as religion, ancestry, and language. One way to understand culture is to look at the values reflected in the actions of individuals and determine how these values are built on the basic assumptions and beliefs of the culture's participants. Other examples include worrying about maintaining harmonious relationships. Respecting each other and maintaining harmonious relations with each other is very important in Asian culture. It is necessary to investigate how the importance of these cultural values plays a role in the medical preferences of patients with chronic diseases. The combination of having basic religious ideas and actively participating in religious activities is what we mean when we talk about someone's religiousness (external). On the other hand, younger patients may have lower rates of adherence to their treatment if they have other responsibilities in their life, such as work or other commitments, which may prevent them from continuing their treatment. Current research demonstrated a significantly beneficial association between institutional religious affiliation and adherence to prescription drugs (odds ratio 1.20, 95 percent confidence interval 1.01–1.14, $P=0.038$). How participation in organizational religious activity promotes commitment is less clear, but one option might be that participation in organizational religious activity reduces sadness levels.

In Koenig et al's research, individuals who are more active in organized religious activities have been shown to have significantly fewer symptoms of depression. Lower rates of depression may be associated with increased drug adherence, as sadness may affect patients' adherence to medication. According to the findings of Grenard et al., a depressed patient was 1.76 times more likely to be non-adherent than the predicted probability of a patient without depression. Consistent with the results of a previous study, a significant reduction in medication adherence was noted over time. Cunico et al. excellent compliance with antihyperlipidemia drugs was noted in 90% of patients during the first 8 months of treatment; however, this percentage dropped to about 80% after 20 months of treatment. These findings indicate that it is necessary to emphasize the importance of maintaining drug compliance over time in patients on long-term drug therapy. Patients' Adaptive Behavior and Belief Patients diagnosed with human immunodeficiency virus had an odds ratio of 9.08, with a 95 percent confidence interval ranging from 3.25 to 25.3, which was statistically significant ($P 0.05$). This was compared to patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease with an odds ratio of 3.25 to 25.3. This may be because

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HIV patients participating in the current study have a realistic understanding of the severity of their condition and the importance of taking their medication as directed. Severity of condition determined by clinical assessment was not associated with patients' compliance behavior, according to the findings of a comprehensive analysis of variables affecting adherence. It was discovered that patients' impressions of the severity of their condition had a significant correlation with medication adherence.

3. Initiative-taking in Their Healthcare

This association has not been shown to be significantly associated with disease severity as determined by clinical examination. Although we included patients who were more initiative-taking in their healthcare, the rate of non-adherence among patients was still unsatisfactory. This is because we have included patients who are more initiative-taking in their healthcare. Second, another issue was the general method used to measure social support levels. Evaluation of specific social support related to drug use, such as practical assistance (for example, helping patients remember to take their prescriptions), may have various effects on adherence, depending on the type of support being measured. Third, the sample size was small and included patients suffering from three different diseases. A final disadvantage was that assessment of patients' adherence to treatment was based solely on self-reports. When using self-report methods, there is a possibility of recall bias that can result in under- or over-reported medication adherence. On the other hand, social support was found to have no significant effect on a patient's ability to take their medication as prescribed. When cultural and religious orientations were examined, it was shown that participation in organizational religious activities affected patients' drug compliance. However, there is no clear explanation for how organizational religious involvement supports drug addiction behavior. Future research may want to explore and determine how this might affect patients' adherence to medication. There has been a substantial amount of research on religious beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors and the factors that may influence them (see Koenig et al., 2012).

This focus has recently become more intense in western countries, because of data showing declining interest in religious belief and activity. For example, surveys conducted in countries

such as the United Kingdom, Western Europe, and the United States have revealed that the general population tends towards a more secular outlook (Office for National Statistics, 2012; Pew Forum on Religion and Public Life , 2014; Chaves, 2017). Twenge and colleagues analyzed data on 11.2 million American adolescents (1966-2014) and found that respondents in the 2010s were significantly less religious than previous generations. This finding was published in the journal Science by Twenge et al., There may be some theoretical and logical basis for their hypothesis stating that there is a correlation between a decrease in religious participation and an increase in individualism (which can be defined as placing greater emphasis on one's own interests rather than the interests of others and society): "... the most important cultural change that has occurred in the United States in the last few decades is the rise in individualism..." (p. 13). The term "locus of control" refers to a distinctive feature of individuals that reveals the extent to which they value individuality (LOC).

According to Rotter (1966), who introduced the construct to the psychological community more than half a century ago, the more individuals perceive the connections between their behavior and its consequences, the more "internal" they become, as opposed to those who are more apt to see. its consequences are determined by luck, fate, luck, or powerful others called "external". The findings of thousands of studies using LOC measures consistent with Rotter's definition provide convincing evidence to suggest that internality is more generally associated with positive outcomes than externality (Rotter, 1966, 1975; Lefcourt, 1976; Nowicki, 2016). One of the questions to be answered in the current research is whether the individual is more likely to engage in religious activity and/or belief, depending on whether they are internally or externally controlled. There is compelling justification from a purely theoretical point of view to account for LOC's relationship to religious belief and behavior. As a generalized "problem solving" expectation that is "triggered" especially when individuals are trying to solve serious problems, Rotter defined reinforcement LOC in social learning theory as a generalized "problem-solving" expectation. As there is no bigger problem than understanding why we exist, individual differences in LOC may very well correlate with differences in religious beliefs and activities. But experts cannot even agree on the direction of the connection. Coursey et al. (2013): "The influence of religion on an individual's sense of personal agency is unclear." Recognition of the presence and influence of a supernatural being in one's life is sometimes accompanied by a dedication to a particular religion. An external form of this concept is

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acceptance of God's will, which can be seen as external control rather than one's own personal or internal control.

On the other hand, there are many who argue that personal control and God's control can coexist if one has a relationship with God characterized by reciprocity (Zahl & Gibson, 2008). Unfortunately, the findings of previous research on religious beliefs and activities and LOC do not provide much help as these studies have also discovered a wide variety of relationships. In other cases, externality (Wiley, 2006), internality (Wigert, 2002), or neither (Lowis et al., 2009) were associated with religiosity. Researchers tend to use various measures of religiosity and LOC as if they were synonymous with each other; this may be one of the factors contributing to the lack of clear and consistent evidence on the relationship between religiosity and LOC. Among other contributors, there is a wide range in age of the participants. Coursey et al. (2013) argued that the internal and external parts of religiosity should be evaluated and investigated independently because they are independent or perpendicular to each other. In other words, the two types of religiosities are in no way related to each other. A belief in the foundations of recognized religion and actions aligned with these ideas are necessary components of inner piety. On the other hand, the term "extrinsic religiosity" refers to the degree to which a person uses religion to achieve non-religious goals such as gaining social support and a sense of community, among other things. These many indicators of religiosity are orthogonal in many respects, and it is inappropriate to use them interchangeably. According to the findings of a meta-analysis (Coursey et al., 2013), there is a significant relationship between religiosity and LOC internality when religiosity is measured on the Rotter scale and religiosity is measured internally. Nowicki and Duke (2016) pointed out that this is a growing problem in all fields of psychology, where the term "locus of control" is literally applied to hundreds of different tests without data to support the appropriate use of the LOC label (Skinner, 1996). This is an example of what Kelley (1927) calls the "Jingle" fallacy, where several tests are used to evaluate the same concept without providing evidence to support this claim. Nowicki et al. (2018) went as far as to recommend that researchers only use tests that give sufficient evidence of construct validity that they are assessing what Rotter describes as a "reinforcement locus of control."

4. Beliefs and Actions

This The recommendation was made in the context of the LOC study. In this, the word "religiousness" is thought of as a summary of beliefs and actions related to religious and spiritual practices. Koenig et al. (2014), religion is a multidimensional construct; it is therefore possible that we are using the term "religiousness" incorrectly here. In conclusion, the primary purpose of the present study was to assess the relationship between LOC as measured by a test that has been shown to be a valid measure of LOC, consistent with Rotter's definition, and participants' self-reported religious beliefs and activities. As determined by both religious service attendance and faith, individuals with high religiosity are expected to have a higher intrinsic LOC than those with low religiosity. This is based on the results of Coursey et al. (2013) showed that in a younger group using Rotter's scale, internality was associated with internal religiosity. When researchers used LOC tests that were structured to be consistent with the structure defined by Rotter, more religiosity as measured by activity within religion was found to be associated with greater internality. This association was found when researchers used LOC tests constructed to be consistent with the construct. This reasoning is consistent with Rotter's social learning theory; This theory is more likely to expect internals than externals to put more effort into their efforts to gather more information, be more persistent, and responsible for whatever problem they are trying to solve. Both religiosity and spirituality, as well as LOC, have been shown to have an impact on behaviors and outcomes related to one's health, which is important to the public health field. To attempt to predict health-related behaviors and outcomes, specific LOC measures have been developed in a variety of different domains, such as health, multidimensional health, and mental health. These scales are often used in short cross-sectional studies, even though Rotter's definition may not be compatible with his results (for review see Timmins and Martin, 2019). As a first step in conducting further research, we explore whether there is a correlation between a broad measure of LOC and religion or spirituality in the ALSPAC longitudinal cohort.

To our knowledge, no one has been able to determine whether the internals or the externals remain more stable in their religious beliefs or actions. Kay et al. (2010) .Internals are expected to be more consistent in their religious beliefs and actions than externals. This is since previous research has found that internals are more likely to stay consistent over time because their

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actions have an impact on what happens to them. This prenatal cohort was created to identify environmental and genetic variables associated with the growth, health, and well-being of children born from the study (Golding and Alspac Study Team, 2004; Boyd et al., 2013; Fraser et al., 2013). Prior to the birth of the child, one of the most important aspects of the research design was collecting data from parents about their personality, feelings, and attitudes, as well as information about themselves, including measurements of their level of consciousness. ALSPAC sought to recruit pregnant women living in Avon, in the southwestern United Kingdom, who were due between 1 April 1991 and 31 December 1992. Comparing census figures in the UK Avon region in 1991 with those in the rest of the country revealed that the demographics of individuals participating in ALSPAC were comparable to those in the UK who were considered to have a small baby (Boyd et al., 2013; Fraser et al., 2013). While the non-religious group is around 10 per cent larger and non-Christian groups slightly less than in the rest of the UK, data collected on religious background as disclosed by ALSPAC in 2001 were included in the UK Census and Bristol County subgroup in 2001 (first population religion was measured in the census) revealed that the results were comparable.

5. Data Collection

Data were collected from this cohort through childhood and adolescence using screenings determined by the child's age. Data collection is ongoing and is done using several methods: self-filled questionnaires (include details of physical and psychological environments, well-being, health, and development); hands-on examination of subjects (includes anthropometry, cardiovascular markers, bone health, and psychiatric interviews); assays of biological samples (includes assays of allergic responses, antibodies indicating recent infections, as well as genetic and epigenetic markers); and link to legal data about individuals. This methodology meant that the study had no knowledge of whether the mother (intentionally) had invited her partner to participate in the study. This was because the mother invited her spouse to participate in the study. As a result, seventy-five percent of the spouses of the women included in the study answered at least one of the questionnaires. Rotter Scale It is linked to the Rotter exam (Nowicki, 2016) and is suitable for assessing people from the general community, as it has an easier reading level than the Rotter scale. ANSIE was implemented in this research project

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using an Anglicized and shorter version of the tool. Based on the results of a pilot study conducted on 135 mothers living in the United States, it consisted of 12 items from the original 40-item scale with the greatest item-total correlation. In the middle of pregnancy, both mom and dad stuffed the scales in their own homes. When factor analysis was performed on the answers received from 12471 female participants, it was determined that the scale had one component. The value of the alpha coefficient in this population is 0.78. Scores ranged from 0 to 12 and were normally distributed, with a median of 4 ($n = 12471$) for mothers and 3 ($n = 8645$) for wives. The higher the score, the more exogenous the LOC. Internal locus of control (ILOC) was defined as scores equal to or lower than the median, while external locus of control (ELOC) was defined as scores above the median.

This definition is consistent with our previous publications (Golding et al., 2017a, b, 2018; Nowicki et al., 2017; Nowicki et al., 2018). Religious Beliefs In collaboration with Ursula King, professor of theology and religious studies at the University of Bristol, and in conversation with Jean Golding, a set of questions was developed specifically for ALSPAC about participants' religious beliefs, attitudes, and Behaviour. Data on participants' religion or beliefs were collected from 9798 couples before pregnancy and from 4484 participants (4059 in both cases) five years later. Variables Related to Demographics The demographic variables used to describe the people participating in the study are the age of the individual's infant at the time of birth; Maximum level of education attained, measured in terms of the UK's national tests or equivalent; whether the mother lives with the child's father; their ethnicity (grouped as white or non-white); birthplaces. Statistical Reviews and Studies This is a descriptive study conducted over an extended period with many participants. This is done in the same way as the pattern search. A binary classification is used to make a comparison between those with internal focus and those with external focus. No statistical adjustments were applied for potential confounders, mediators, or moderators, as the aim was to provide a clear account of the link between various aspects of religious belief and action and the LOC. In fact, distinguishing between them is not a simple task. For example, there is substantial evidence to suggest that the attitudes and actions of an extroverted teenager are associated with lower levels of educational achievement and thus often lower levels of professional achievement (Floury, 2006). Thus, allowing such social characteristics would be tantamount to allowing the LOC itself, resulting in the elimination of evidence for a link with the LOC. Results Historical and Population Data Table 1 shows the

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different demographic backgrounds of the people who participated in the study and answered the questions according to their level of religiosity. As expected, men are slightly more likely to fall into the older age group, slightly more likely to have better educational credentials, and slightly more likely to be people of color. It is possible that the mother did not give the questionnaire to her spouse, which may explain why fathers of children who do not live with their mothers are less likely to be involved. Overall, the study area produced slightly more women than men (56.0 per cent of women and 51.3 per cent of men), but the rest of the UK produced significantly more men (44.3 per cent of men and 51.3 per cent of women). 38.9 percent).

There was no noticeable difference according to the gender of the child. There were significant differences in responses from male and female participants in the study. About half of women (49.9 percent) said they believed in God or another divine being, which is much higher than the proportion of men who hold this belief (36.9 percent; $P < 0.001$). A similar percentage of people who identified as agnostic (answering "not sure"), but the percentage of men who identified as atheist (answered "no belief") was significantly higher than the proportion of women (14.9 percent versus 28.6 percent; $P < 0.001$). In line with these findings, men were less likely to say that a divine presence was helping them, were less likely to pray to God when they were in distress, were less likely and less likely to attend religious ceremonies. In terms of religious affiliation, although proportionately more women than men indicated affiliation with a Christian religion (80.4% women, 68.8% men), slightly more men affiliated with a non-Christian religion (5.4 percent.) men, 4.2 percent women). As would be expected based on the belief data presented earlier, the most significant difference between the sexes was in those who claimed to have no relationship (15.4 percent women, 25.8 percent men).non-believers were least likely to have an intrinsic orientation (atheists). The difference between those who believed in something and those who were unsure about it was much greater than the difference between those who were unsure about something and those who did not believe anything. Members of Religions Those who had an experience of feeling that a divine power was helping them and those who prayed to God during tough times showed a similar trend in the proportion of internally oriented individuals. Again, the difference between those who responded affirmatively and those who were undecided was much larger than the difference between those who were skeptical and those who responded negatively. There were significant differences in

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the orientation of those who received support from members of their own religion and those who received support from members of other faiths; Those who went to the place of worship, even once a year, were thought to have a higher level of spirituality than those who did not. When asked about a plan of action they might need in the future, those who said they would pray to God in times of difficulty were more introverted, as were those who were unsure of their plans. On the other hand, those who said they would not pray to God, or any other celestial power were significantly more likely to have an outward-oriented worldview (data not shown). Those who identified themselves as belonging to a religion other than Christianity were more focused on their inner lives than those who did not claim to be Christian or religious.

Both mothers and fathers in the study exhibited the same recurring patterns throughout their lives. There was an interesting correlation with the length of time an individual held a particular belief; Those who stated that they had been for more than 5 years (but not lifetime) were more likely to be internalized than those whose beliefs had been evident for less than 5 years. This was so because of an interesting relationship to the length of time an individual held a particular belief. Where Does Control Lie and How Can Religious Beliefs Evolve? 26.8 percent of women and 29.3 percent of men reported changing their belief category (i.e., from believer to agnostic or atheist) between their pregnancy and the age of their children. Using parents as participants in a large longitudinal study, the following can be shown about this population: In this population, more women than men reported belief in God or a divine being; On the other hand, men stated that they did not have more faith than women. People who are more introverted are more likely to believe, go to places of worship, and receive support from other faiths as well as their own religion, compared to extroverted individuals. In this Christian society, those who declared their allegiance to a faith other than Christianity were more inward-focused than their Christian counterparts. Over the six years of the study, introverts had more consistency in their views than extroverts. Overall, while the percentage of believers in this parent group decreased over time, there was an increase in the number of unbelievers in this group. Overall, the relationships between LOC and measures of religiosity are comparable between men and women. This was also true for the entire population. In a sample of people not selected for religion, co-morbidity, education, or occupation, this study is, to our knowledge, the largest ever to explore links between religiosity and LOC. As discovered by previous researchers, women have been shown to have greater degrees of religiosity and to be more external than

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men (Fiori et al., 2006; Coursey et al., 2013). Coursey et al. (2013) were confirmed in their meta-analysis when they found that greater interiority than exteriority was associated with stronger religious belief and greater participation in a place of worship. Numerous studies have shown associations between internality and outcomes, such as higher academic achievement (eg, Flouri, 2006; Shepherd et al., 2006), higher athletic achievement (eg, Arnaud et al., 2012), and achievement and (eg, Arnaud et al., 2012). . ., Arnaud et al., 2012) explain the importance of the concept of LOC. These studies can be found in Flouri (2006), Shepherd e (e.g., Kormanik and Rocco, 2009; Wu et al., 2015). In contrast, externality is associated with increases in anxiety (Carden et al., 2004), sadness (Bjrkklf et al., 2013), negative personality traits (Nowicki and Duke, 1974; Wheeler and White, 1991), and psychoses (Nowicki) (Duke, 1974; Wheeler and White, 1991). (Harrow et al., 2009; Weintraub et al., 2016). Rotter thought of LOC as a learned, generalized problem-solving expectation that demonstrates how essential people believe their efforts are in addressing existential challenges in the context of academic, social, or current debate. Considerable evidence lends credence to the hypothesis that insiders are better equipped than outsiders to address real-world academic and social challenges (for example, Nowicki and Duke, 1983; Nowicki and Duke, 2016).

On the other hand, the more general issue of how internals and externals approach the "problem" of existence has received far less attention than it deserves. The findings of the current research begin to fill some gaps in knowledge about how internal and external persons approach the challenge of dealing with the issue of internal beliefs. Internals give the impression of having more consistent and enthusiastic religious views than externals and are also more likely to engage in religious activities. The correlation between LOC and measures of extrinsic religiosity should be further investigated in the future before it can be evaluated. It is possible that the relationship between extrinsic religiosity and LOC is represented differently in the United Kingdom and the United States.

6. Results

Extrinsic religiosity is a measure of how people use religion to achieve social goals regardless of belief. As a component of the UK education system, primary schools may be affiliated with

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a particular religion (in the Avon area, this could be the Church of England or the Roman Catholic Church) and the school is proof that prospective parents attend the church to which the school is affiliated. This could potentially introduce an unknown bias to study results, and this is something that should be explored in further research. The very large representative sample of participants (approximately 20,000 men and women) in terms of the diversity of social and environmental contexts is one of the most obvious benefits of this research: General population, evaluation of pregnant women. Researchers have not investigated age as a potential mediator component in eating disorders; however, the onset of eating disorders usually occurs between the initial stages of adolescence and early adulthood.

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